

EIC User Group Newsletter

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Prepared by

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NEWS

- The **next EIC Users Group Meeting ([EICUGM 2020](#))**, originally scheduled in Miami on 3-7 August, will be held **online on 15-17 July**. The tentative programme of the **first day** will list in the morning **updates** about EIC project, machine design and software, followed in the afternoon by presentations from **US DOE and NFS**, as well as from **country/community representatives from Europe and India**. The morning of the **second day** will be devoted to the **IB general meeting**, including discussion on the [EoI process](#) and brief presentations from interested groups/consortia (contact [Christine Aidala](#), IB Chair, or [Andrea Bressan](#), IB Vice-Chair, by 10 July if willing to give a presentation); if time permits, there will be also a discussion on future Collaborations formation in 2021. The **rest of the time** will be taken by parallel sessions for the **Yellow Report Physics and Detector Working Groups**.
- On Friday 19 June, 11am CERN time, the final **European Strategy Report** was publicly presented and unanimously adopted by the CERN Council. The **slides** presented by the Secretary of the Strategy Update, Halina Abramowicz, can be found at this [link](#) . The **Strategy recommendations** can be found [here](#), and the related **deliberation document** is [here](#) . The **EIC project is positively represented**, and **support** to European contributions to global facilities outside Europe is explicitly mentioned as an optional decision of CERN Council, and as a planned initiative of **NuPECC** for the specific case of the EIC in United States.

- **US projects**, like the EIC, need to pass some formal project milestones, or “**critical decisions**”. Here is the official [DOE Order 413.3B](#) about an overview of the subject. For the convenience of the non-US scientists, [here](#) is a short overview by Rolf Ent of the rationale for the various steps.
- In the “[Yellow Report](#)” [menu of the EICUG web page](#), one can find the **calendar** of the next “**Yellow Report**” **workshops**, that will both be held **online**:
 3. 17-19 September 2020, CUA - Washington D.C. (USA)
 4. 19-21 November 2020, UCB - Berkeley (USA)

NEWS from the CHARTER COMMITTEE

- The Charter Committee has prepared a **survey** on the EICUG organizational structure, on effectiveness of communications and meetings, on responsibility of membership, on voting procedures, etc.. The draft of the survey has been finalized; the document will be distributed to the whole EICUG in due time.

NEWS from the ELECTION & NOMINATION COMMITTEE

- The elections for the office of **International Representative** on the EICUG Steering Committee have been closed by the end of June. There are **two candidates**: Wouter Deconinck (Univ. Manitoba - Canada), Bedanga Mohanty (National Institute of Science and Education Research - NISER, India). The Election & Nomination Committee will soon communicate the final result.

NEWS from the CONFERENCE & TALKS COMMITTEE

- Because of the Covid-19 lockdown, the **schedule** of next workshops and summer schools of interest for the EICUG has been **drastically modified**: many events have been **postponed** (sometimes with tentative dates), have **become on-line** meetings, or have been **cancelled** completely (see below). Thus, the speaking opportunities on behalf of the EICUG have been reduced. Nevertheless, there are **still two open slots** available:
 1. ICHEP 2020, 28 July - 6 Aug 2020, on-line, parallel session
 2. IWHSS 2020, 16-20 Nov 2020, (Trieste, Italy), plenary session, not clear if on-line or in-person meeting
- In any case, for consulting the list of **open EICUG talks** see <http://www.eicug.org/web/events/open> . For a list of **previous EICUG talks** see <http://www.eicug.org/web/events/previous> (often including also a link to the presentation). If you wish to recommend a candidate, including yourself, or if in general you wish to suggest new speakers (including yourself) to be considered for future invitations, please contact the Conference & Talks Committee at eicug-talks@eicug.org . Here, you can find also the general [talks guidelines](#) .

NEWS from the SOFTWARE WORKING GROUP

- Starting from June 2020, The Software WG will share **Software news on a monthly basis**. The **June issue** of the bulletin can be found [here](#). For more frequent updates, please consider subscribing to the mailing list of the Software WG: eicug-software@eicug.org .

NEWS from the INSTITUTIONAL BOARD

- The **EICUG** currently stands at **1085 members**, from **228 institutions** in 31 countries. Theory members are approximately 25%, experimentalists 60%, experts in accelerators 14%, support 1%.

This is a pie chart illustrating how the 228 EICUG Institutions are split into the 6 world regions.

- Since last issue of the Newsletter, four more institutions joined the EICUG:
 - * Central University of Karnataka (India)
 - * University of Jammu (India)
 - * Malaviya National Institute of Technology, Jaipur (India)
 - * Ramakrishna Mission Residential College, Narendrapur (India)

RECENT WORKSHOPS/MEETINGS of INTEREST

See also <http://www.eicug.org/web/events/previous> (includes also links to some presentations)

Those events labeled by were held with on-line only format.

[Jet observables at an Electron Ion Collider](#), Upton (NY - US), 15-17 April 2020 **Cancelled**

[Streaming Readout VI](#), 13-15 May 2020

[2nd EIC Physics and Detector Conceptual Development Workshop](#), Pavia (Italy), 22-24 May 2020

[Hard Probes](#), Austin (TX - USA), 31 May - 5 June 2020

[Workshop on Pion and Kaon Structure Functions at the EIC](#), CFNS-Stony Brook (NY-US), 2-5 June 2020

UPCOMING WORKSHOPS/MEETINGS of INTEREST

See also <http://www.eicug.org/web/events/upcoming> and <http://cnr2.kent.edu/~manley/BRAGmeetings.html> (the latter is temporarily not updated due to the current “stay at home” order)

The events labeled by will be held only on-line. If joined by “?”, it means that a decision is not yet taken.

[Origin of the Visible Universe: Unraveling the Proton Mass \(INT-20-77W\)](#), INT Seattle (WA - US), 4 - 8 May 2020 **Postponed**

[Transversity 2020](#), Pavia (Italy), 25-29 May 2020
Postponed to May 2021

[Joint GlueX-PANDA-EIC Workshop on Machine Learning for Particle Physics Experiments](#), Darmstadt (Germany), 25-29 May 2020 **Postponed**

[Tomography of light nuclei at an EIC](#), ECT*-Trento (Italy), 15-19 June 2020 **Postponed** to 25-29 October 2021

[LXX International Conference NUCLEUS-2020](#), Saint Petersburg (Russia), 26-30 June 2020 **Postponed** to 11-17 October 2020 ?

[Light-Cone 2020](#), Jeju (Korea), 29 June - 4 July 2020
Postponed to 14-18 December 2020

[Beam polarization and polarimetry at EIC](#), CFNS-Stony Brook (NY-US), 26 June, 29 June, 1 July, 2020

[Ad-hoc Meeting: Radiative Corrections](#), Stony Brook, 9-10 July 2020

[EIC Users Group Meeting 2020](#), Miami, 15-17 July 2020

[9th International Conference on New Frontiers in Physics \(ICNFP 2020\)](#), Kolymbari (Crete - Greece), 4 - 12 September 2020

[40th International Conference on High Energy Physics \(ICHEP 2020\)](#), Prague (Czech Republic), 28 July - 6 August 2020

[Photonuclear Gordon Conference](#), Holderness (NH - USA), 9-14 August 2020 **Cancelled**

[22nd International Conference on Particles and Nuclei \(PANIC2020\)](#),
Lisbon (Portugal), 31 August - 4 September 2020
Postponed to 30 August - 3 September 2021

[24th International Spin Symposium SPIN2020](#), Matsue (Japan), 20-25
September 2020 **Postponed** to fall 2021

[Baryon 2020](#), Sevilla (Spain), 22-25 September 2020
Postponed to 19-22 October 2021

[New Physics Phenomena - Hadronic Contributions to New Physics
Searches](#), Crete (Greece), 24-30 September 2020

[APS DNP Fall meeting](#), New Orleans (LA - USA), 29 October - 1
November 2020

[The 17th International Workshop on Hadron Structure and
Spectroscopy](#), Trieste (Italy), 16-20 November 2020

[8th International Conference on High Energy Physics in the LHC era](#),
Valparaiso (Chile), 4-8 January 2021

[Lepton-Photon 2021](#), Manchester (UK), 9-14 August 2021

Quarks and Nucleon Physics QNP 2021, Bonn (Germany), 20-24
September 2021

UPCOMING SCHOOLS of INTEREST

[HUGS 2020](#), JLab-Newport News (VA-US), 1-19 June 2020 **Cancelled**

[National Nuclear Physics Summer School 2020](#), UNAM-Mexico City (Mexico), 22 June - 2 July 2020

[The Second CFNS Summer School on the Science of the Future Electron-Ion Collider](#), CFNS-Stony Brook (NY-US), 27 July - 5 August 2020
Cancelled

[Hadron Collider Physics Summer School](#), Fermilab-CERN,
10-21 August 2020

[MCnet-CTEQ Summer School 2020](#), Bad Herrenalb (Germany), 2-12 August 2020 **Cancelled**

[International School for Strangeness Nuclear Physics](#)
(SNP2020), J-PARC, Tokai (Japan), 2-5 December 2020

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